

RESPONSIBLE AUTHORSHIP: TU WIEN GOOD PRACTICE GUIDANCE

WHAT IS AUTHORSHIP

The aim of identifying authors and assigning authorship is primarily to allow researchers to get credit for their work, but also to create transparency for readers with regard to who is responsible for the work that has been produced. Conflicts in determining authorship are not uncommon, and this topic is one of the research integrity issues most frequently discussed among researchers. This guidance document focuses on good practices around authorship and provides practical recommendations and helpful tips for avoiding typical pitfalls. It also provides information for you as a member of the TU Wien research community on where to seek additional support with regard to questions on authorship.

Author

The author of an academic or scientific work can be anyone who has made a significant intellectual contribution to the study. While publishing journals lay down the general rules for authorship, it is the responsibility of the individuals who conduct the work and intend to publish it to determine who deserves credit as an author and bears responsibility for the work¹. The intellectual contribution can be considered in different ways, and relates to the initial formulation of important activities in the elaboration of a publication, as in the generation of research ideas, the development of a methodical design, the collection of data and their analysis, the drafting of the manuscript, its revision or final approval.

Other collaborators who contribute to the work but do so in ways which cannot be considered substantive, and therefore do not meet the requirements mentioned above, should be acknowledged for their contributions but not given credit as authors. Examples of activities to be acknowledged include translation, language editing and proofreading, technical help, data collection, provision of samples, or funding acquisition.

In the case of manuscripts authored by a group, it is recommended that all individual authors as well as the group name are indicated. Usually the list other members of the group are mentioned in the Acknowledgments section.

¹ See the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE). Roles and Responsibilities of Authors, Contributors, Reviewers, Editors, Publishers, and Owners. 2021.
<http://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role-of-authors-and-contributors.html>

According to the following criteria, proposed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) in 2003², “authorship credit should be based only on:

- (1) substantial contributions to conception and design, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data; AND
- (2) drafting the article or revising it critically for important intellectual content; AND
- (3) final approval of the version to be published”.

All these three conditions must be met simultaneously. It is important to bear in mind that activities such as acquisition of funding, collection of data, or general supervision of the research group do not justify authorship.

Similarly, the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE)³ guidelines are broader than those of COPE and recommend that authors state their contribution to the project, providing a description of the roles for each individual. This increases transparency about the involvement of each author in a published work, reduces the chances of disputes, and avoids unethical behaviours and misconduct. ICMJE recommends that authorship should be based on the following 4 criteria:

- (1) substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; AND
- (2) drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content; AND
- (3) final approval of the version to be published; AND
- (4) agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

These guidelines also highlight that those contributors who have made substantive intellectual contributions to a paper should be given credit as authors; concurrently, all contributors credited as authors need to take responsibility and be accountable for what is published.

Role of the corresponding author

Following the ICMJE definition, the corresponding author is the person designated as the primarily responsible person as well as contact person for the content and process of the publication. The corresponding author must ensure that those who have authored the work have reviewed and approved the final version of the research output. They also handle the communication throughout the submission and peer review process, as well as the response to inquiries after the manuscript is published. These tasks may depend on the journal’s requirements or particular disciplinary requirements (i.e. clinical trial registration documentation, ethics committee approval, etc.).

² Albert T, and Wager E, on behalf of COPE Council. How to handle authorship disputes: a guide for new researchers. Version 1. September 2003. <https://doi.org/10.24318/cope.2018.1.1>

³ See footnote 1

Order of the authors

As in many other aspects of academic publishing, the order of the authors may have a different meaning depending on the academic discipline. In some domains, such as biomedicine and natural sciences, the first author is usually the researcher who conducted most of the research (e.g. running experiments/studies/surveys) and wrote a draft of the manuscript. In these disciplines the last author position indicates a responsible role in overseeing the research team. In other disciplines, however, authors are listed in alphabetical order with no particular meaning attached to any given position. Therefore, depending on the subject area, the order of authors has to be considered when defining a publication authorship. This may be particularly important in multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary collaboration where different disciplinary practices and cultures meet.

AUTHOR AND NON-AUTHOR CONTRIBUTORSHIPS

In order to normalise the different categories of research output contributions, in 2012 a group of editors and researchers⁴ introduced the CRediT Taxonomy (Contributor Roles Taxonomy)⁵. Currently, CRediT is managed as an informal standard at CASRAI⁶ and has been widely adopted since 2014 across many publishers and institutions to improve accessibility and visibility of the variety of contributions to research outputs.

CRediT comprises 14 roles that represent the following typical activities involved in a scientific scholarly output:

- Conceptualisation – ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.
- Methodology – development or design of methodology; creation of models.
- Software – programming, software development; designing computer programmes; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.
- Validation – verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.
- Formal analysis – application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesise study data.
- Investigation – conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.
- Resources – provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools.

⁴ IWCSA Report (2012). Report on the International Workshop on Contributorship and Scholarly Attribution, May 16, 2012. Harvard University and the Wellcome Trust. http://projects.iq.harvard.edu/attribution_workshop

⁵ CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy). <https://casrai.org/credit/>

⁶ Consortia Advancing Standards in Research Administration Information (CASRAI). <https://casrai.org/>

- Data curation – management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data, and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later re-use.
- Writing – original draft – preparation, creation, and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).
- Writing – review & editing – preparation, creation, and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary, or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.
- Visualisation – preparation, creation, and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualisation/data presentation.
- Supervision – oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team.
- Project administration – management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution
- Funding acquisition – acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication

The use of CRediT does not change the basic above-mentioned criteria behind the constitution of authorship, but it simplifies the categorisation and helps all individuals to receive a fair recognition of their personal contribution without risking any authorship-related disputes.

Many publishers also recommend or even require authors to include contribution statements in the work that specify the contribution of every author in order to promote transparency. Initials are used to refer to each author's contributions. An example are the Author contribution statements of the Nature Portfolio journals' authorship policy⁷.

GOOD PRACTICE RECOMMENDATIONS

- Ideally, the decision of the inclusion and order of authors should take place at the beginning of the project or when planning a publication. The envisaged contributions of the different people involved in the work should be considered at this point. Open communication about roles and contributions in the beginning can prevent misunderstandings once the work is about to be published. This is a collective responsibility of all researchers engaged in the work to be published.
- Consult and follow well-established guidelines for determining authorship, such as the ICMJE and COPE guidelines and the requirements for determining authorship established by the journal that you intend to publish in, as explained above (see footnote 1).
- If a person has contributed to a publication according to relevant criteria for authorship, their name must be included in the list of authors.
- The order of the authors should follow the conventions in the given discipline(s). Make sure this point is openly discussed early on especially when working in multidisciplinary teams.

⁷ Author contribution statements. Nature Portfolio journals' authorship policy <https://www.nature.com/nature-portfolio/editorial-policies/authorship#author-contribution-statements>

- The CRediT taxonomy should be used to specify the individual contribution of the authors of a research output, and also to acknowledge additional contributions by individuals contributing to the research with activities that otherwise would not be perceptible.
- All contributions should be acknowledged, whether from those listed as authors or from individuals named in the acknowledgements section. Individual contributors can be assigned multiple roles, and a given role can be assigned to multiple contributors. Where multiple individuals serve in the same role, the degree of contribution can optionally be specified as 'lead', 'equal', or 'supporting'.
- The acknowledgements section is an appropriate place to thank your collaborators who have not participated in a way that merits authorship.
- In the case of a corporate or group authorship (e.g. working group), all collaborators' names should be listed.
- Each author and contributor should use an Open Researcher and Contributor (ORCID) iD⁸ as persistent unique identifier to avoid name ambiguity and to help both authors and contributors to get the full credit for their contribution to a work.

PRACTICES TO BE AVOIDED

- Participation in obtaining resources, collecting data or samples, recruiting experimental subjects, performing administration activities, preparing data, or reviewing the manuscript does not justify being credited co-authorship.
- The omission of the name of a person who has contributed in a publication according to the criteria mentioned above would constitute unethical conduct and breach of research integrity and intellectual property rights.
- The inclusion of a person as an author of a publication based on their hierarchical position (resulting in "gift", "guest", "courtesy" or "honorary" authorship) is unethical and might pose an unacceptable abuse of authority and could represent research misconduct.
- Artificially sharing first or last authorship between two authors or having two corresponding authors, should be avoided.

HOW TO SPECIFY AUTHORSHIP AND CONTRIBUTORSHIP

In order to show how authorship and contributorship can be illustrated and credit appropriately assigned, some examples of authors' contributions statements are shown below.

If CRediT is used, the following possibilities to describe individual effort can be helpful:

- "ML: Conceptualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. RR: Conceptualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. JF: Conceptualisation, Supervision."
- "PA: Review and editing (equal). KJ: Conceptualisation (lead); writing – original draft (lead); formal analysis (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). ER: Software (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). HW: Methodology (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). JU:

⁸ ORCID. <https://orcid.org/>

Conceptualisation (supporting); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal).”

- "Conceptualisation, EJ and AY; Methodology, EJ; Software, EJ; Validation, EJ, YY and MR; Formal Analysis, EJ; Investigation, EJ; Resources, EJ; Data Curation, MR; Writing – original draft Preparation, AY; Writing – review & editing, EJ.; Visualisation, EJ; Supervision, EJ; Project administration, EJ; Funding acquisition, AY”

If CRediT is not used and the authors wish to or are required to specify concrete tasks in conducting the research, the attribution of contribution could be as follows:

- “AC, TK and BN conceived this research and designed experiments; JY participated in the design and interpretation of the data; TM performed experiments and analysis; AC and TK wrote the paper and participated in the revisions of it. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.”
- "FC analysed and interpreted the patient data regarding the hematological disease and the transplant. RH performed the histological examination of the kidney, and was a major contributor in writing the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.”
- “All authors contributed to the design and implementation of the system or analysis and interpretation of associated data. NMS led the research on the ground. BJB designed the data management system and developed systems for the printing of ID cards, automatic data downloading and processing. AS and SJ took responsibility for data management electronic form development on the ground. BJB and SS developed the performance monitoring system. BPS managed the field team under the overall management of DSM. AMPB and JSW inputted on the content and field-testing of questionnaires. AC participated in the study design and coordination. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.”
- “EGR constructed the Bayesian adaptive designs, ran the simulations of the designs, applied the designs to the trial data and drafted the manuscript; SG directed the research; NS, RL, CJ and SG designed and analysed the original trial; and GDP and SG were the Chief Investigators of the PARAMEDIC2 trial. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.”
- “R.A., R.P.G., and H.R.K. conceived the work with contributions from all authors; R.A. prepared the first draft with contributions from H.R.K., R.L., and R.P.G.; all authors substantially contributed to the final manuscript.”
- "Both (All) authors have contributed equally to the work.”

If you need further information or have potential matters of concern, you can contact the library for information regarding general questions around authorship practices.

If you need an impartial and confidential consultation concerning an authorship issue or if you find yourself in a conflict situation, you can get in touch with the research ethics coordinator.

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